

Get Involved

- Join our mailing list:
ehealth@ul.ie
- www.ehealth4cancer.ie
- Join the OHDSI MStTeams community and subscribe to OHDSI working groups

Everyone is welcome to actively participate in **OHDSI**, whether you are a patient, a health professional, a researcher, or someone who simply believes in our cause. Join our growing community and help advance real-world evidence research in Ireland.

More
Information
on our
website:

Leadership

Aedin Culhane
University of Limerick

Mark Lawlor
Queens University, Belfast

Catherine Mahoney
Eli Lilly and Company

OHDSI Ireland was established by representatives from **7** universities, **8** academic teaching hospitals, **2** government/public health agencies, and industry members from **4** pharmaceutical companies, **2** tech firms and **1** genomics services company.

OHDSI IRELAND

The all-island Irish National Node fostering real-world evidence research, advancing healthcare outcomes, and building collaborative partnerships across Ireland.

Our Objectives

The OHDSI Ireland node is established with clear goals to transform healthcare research and policy through collaborative real-world evidence generation.

Foster Collaboration

Facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing, fostering real-world evidence research on the island of Ireland through multi-stakeholder engagement.

Align with National Initiatives

Align with national health initiatives and stimulate research collaborations and projects with European and global OHDSI partners.

Enhance Communication

Communicate OHDSI activities and facilitate engagement with OHDSI working groups, meetings, and events across the research community.

What is OHDSI?

The Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (or OHDSI, pronounced "Odyssey") global multi-stakeholder, community develop the use of the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) and open-source solutions to standardise diverse health databases, enabling large-scale, reproducible research across institutions and borders while allowing data holders to maintain control. The network brings together researchers, clinicians, industry partners, and regulators worldwide, allowing institutions to collaborate while retaining control of their local data. Its goal is to generate reliable real-world evidence to improve health decisions and care.

Learn more about OHDSI:

Glossary

EHDS (European Health Data Space):

An EU framework (Regulation 2025/327) that enables secure sharing of health data for healthcare (primary use) and for research, policy, and regulation (secondary use), while ensuring strong privacy and patient control.

Interoperability:

The ability of different health information systems, software, and devices to exchange, interpret, and use data seamlessly across organizational or national boundaries.

OMOP-CDM (Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership – Common Data Model):

A standardized data model developed by the OHDSI community to harmonize the structure and content of diverse healthcare databases. It enables large-scale, reproducible research across different systems and countries by transforming data into a common format.

Real-world data (RWD)

Health data collected as part of clinical care including electronic health records, insurance claims data, or patient registries.

RWE (Real-World Evidence):

Clinical or health-related insights derived from analysing real-world data (RWD).

Federated Data Analysis :

A method of analysing data that is distributed across multiple sources or locations, without moving the data to a central repository, and only algorithms or aggregated results are shared.